

Climate-friendly and resilient fisheries
through innovation and co-learning

infinifish.eu

Plans for testing and validation of the ten Infinifish solutions

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About Infinifish

The project *Climate-friendly and resilient fisheries through innovation and co-learning*, short name *Infinifish*, is an innovation action funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research programme under Grant Agreement number 101181077. Its objective is to create innovations to monitor and mitigate the impacts of fishing on the climate and enable fishers to adapt to the consequences of climate change. To learn more about the project, its participants, and its results, please visit the Infinifish web site at <https://infinifish.eu> and the CORDIS project fact sheet and results database at <https://doi.org/10.3030/101181077>.

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the **detailed testing and validation plan implemented by 11 pilot cases for the 10 Infinifish solutions**, aimed at improving operational efficiency, sustainability, and circularity across fisheries. The solutions cover decision support systems (InfiniLog, InfiniCatch Jano, InfiniCatch Trawl, InfiniCatch NOR), fishing gears (InfiniDoor, InfiniWing), robotic fish handling (InfiniSort), and fish processing and valorisation (InfiniSile, InfiniFood, InfiniGrow). For each solution, the document provides an **integrated framework** for evaluation, outlining their **operational context, testing objectives, expected outputs, data collection and management procedures, and risk mitigation measures**.

Data collection is designed to combine historical records, real-time onboard sensors, laboratory analyses, and controlled experimental conditions, ensuring robust, high-quality datasets suitable for model development, solution optimisation, and performance evaluation. The plan includes structured feedback loops for iterative improvement of each solution, incorporating both empirical data and end-user input. Key challenges identified include variability in operational environments, equipment reliability, data quality, and stakeholder engagement. Mitigation strategies address these challenges through pre-testing of hardware and software, structured monitoring, iterative development, stakeholder briefing, and flexible scheduling.

The deliverable concludes with a brief overview of general findings, challenges and risks, and the timeline for advancing from controlled trials to full operational validation. The planned testing activities will deliver validated solutions, high-quality datasets, and actionable guidance for scaling and adoption. **These outcomes aim to provide fisheries operators with tools for improved decision-making, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced resource valorisation, contributing to more sustainable and efficient fisheries.**

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIS	Automatic identification system
CPUE	Catch per unit effort
DSS	Decision support systems
EEA	European economic area
EM	Electronic monitoring
ERS	Electronic reporting systems
FUE	Fuel use efficiency
FUI	Fuel use intensity
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
LAB	Lactic acid bacteria
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry
NIS	Non-indigenous species
RPM	Revolution per minute
TAC	Total allowable catches
TBARS	Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances
TPA	Texture profile analysis
TRL	Technology readiness level
TVB-N	Total volatile basic nitrogen
TVC	Total viable counts
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the detailed testing and validation plans developed under Work Package 4 (WP4) of the Infinifish project. WP4 is responsible for the systematic evaluation, validation, and iterative refinement of the technological and methodological solutions developed in WP3. Its role is to ensure that these solutions are assessed under realistic operational conditions and in alignment with the project's objectives, expected impacts, and stakeholder needs.

Figure 1-1: Geographical distribution of Infinifish pilot activities across Europe, illustrating the integration of decision support systems, smart fishing gear innovations, automated fish processing technologies, and novel seafood product developments.

Within Infinifish, ten solutions are being developed across four main domains: decision support systems (DSS), fishing gears, robotic fish handling, and fish processing. These solutions will be tested and validated through eleven pilot cases distributed across multiple European sea basins and fisheries contexts. Testing activities are conducted both on board fishing vessels and in onshore environments, thereby covering different stages of the fisheries value chain, from capture operations to post-harvest handling and processing (Figure 1-1).

The primary purpose of this deliverable is to describe how each solution will be tested and validated. It consolidates the planned testing activities for all solutions,

detailing their operational contexts, validation objectives, data collection and analysis approaches, and identified risks and mitigation measures. As such, this document provides a forward-looking and structured framework for evidence generation. The outcomes of WP4 testing activities will directly inform iterative refinement of the solutions developed in WP3, while also contributing to the co-learning processes in WP5 and the broader impact assessment and scalability analyses in WP6.

Several of the WP4 pilot cases are closely aligned with social case studies that will be conducted in WP5, which examine the social, economic, and governance conditions that influence the uptake of the Infinifish solutions. In total, 9 social case studies will be executed and correspond with the WP4 pilot cases across different fisheries and regions. These social case studies are grouped in three overarching theme studies. Table 1-1 represents an overview of the social case studies and their alignment with the WP4 pilot cases, which is intentional as it enables interactions between technical testing and stakeholder engagement activities. Insights from WP4 trials will inform discussions in WP5 workshops, whilst stakeholder feedback gathered through WP5 will provide contextual insights that may support interpretation of testing results and inform further solution development. More information and details on the social data collection approach within WP5 are provided in Deliverable 5.1, Social data collection plan.

Table 1-1: Overview of the WP5 social case studies.

Theme study	Focus area	Social case study
Mitigation technologies	Adoption of gear innovations to reduce fuel use and seabed impact	InfiniWing, Celtic Sea demersal trawling
		InfiniDoor, North Sea and Skagerrak Nephrops trawling
		InfiniDoor, Mediterranean and Black Sea whitefish trawling
Optimising systems	Decision support tools for improving efficiency and reducing fuel intensity	InfiniCatch Trawl, Northeast Atlantic large-scale demersal fisheries
		InfiniCatch NOR, Northeast Atlantic small-scale and large-scale fisheries
		InfiniCatch Jano & InfiniLog, Bay of Biscay pelagic fisheries

Enhanced utilisation	Processing and utilisation technologies addressing shifts in fish stocks	InfiniFood, Mediterranean and Black Sea small-scale fisheries
		InfiniGrow, Mediterranean and Black Sea small-scale fisheries
		InfiniSort, Northeast Atlantic whitefish fisheries

This deliverable is structured as follows: **Section 1** introduces the scope and objectives of WP4 and outlines the role of testing and validation within the Infinifish project. **Section 2** provides an overview of the ten solutions developed within WP3, including their main characteristics, responsible partners, and planned Technology Readiness Level (TRL) progression. **Section 3** presents the detailed solution-specific testing and validation plans, organised into the four different domains of the solutions: DSS, fishing gears, robotic fish handling, and fish processing. For each solution, the operational context, testing objectives, data collection and analysis approach, and identified risks and mitigation measures are described. Finally, **Section 4** synthesises general findings across solutions, highlights cross-cutting challenges and risks, and outlines the timeline and next steps for WP4 implementation.

2 Solutions overview

Table 2-1 provides an overview of the ten WP3 solutions subject to testing and validation within WP4. For each solution, the table summarises its core functionality and scope, identifies the responsible partner(s), and specifies both the TRL at project start and the expected TRL at project completion. The indicated TRL progression reflects the advancement foreseen in the project proposal and is linked to the progressive maturation of each solution through prototype refinement, pilot-scale demonstration, and validation under operational conditions.

As outlined in the introduction, the solutions span four functional domains within the fisheries value chain. The DSS (green) include InfiniLog, InfiniCatch Jano, InfiniCatch Trawl, and InfiniCatch NOR; the fishing gear innovations (blue) comprise InfiniWing and InfiniDoor; the robotic fish handling technologies (yellow) include InfiniSort; and the fish processing and valorisation solutions (orange) comprise InfiniSile, InfiniFood, and InfiniGrow.

Table 2-1: Overview of WP3 solutions subject to testing and validation in WP4, including responsible partners and TRL progression (base and expected).

Solution	Description	Partners	Baseline TRL	Expected TRL
InfiniLog	Network datalogger solution for collecting data from different sensors and systems on board vessels. The software enables interfacing a variety of data providers using different protocols and connections.	SO, AZTI	5	7
InfiniCatch Jano	DSS based on a set of models for climate change mitigation and adaptation on board, served at a near-real-time basis from onshore AI servers. These include routing, best-place-to-fish, shifting species, estimated time of arrival and associated fuel consumption, and expected price – all of them served from cloud servers to a dedicated display on board.	AZTI, SILECMAR	5	7
InfiniCatch Trawl	A data collection system and software platform that can be installed on any vessel equipped with electronic winches. It integrates with standard	HAFRO, Naust Marine, Trackwell	5-6	7

	Icelandic logbook software and commonly available sensors to record the geometry of trawl fishing gear.			
InfiniCatch NOR	Integration of new algorithms and methods into Catchwise's existing DSS to improve catch efficiency and reduce GHG emissions.	Catchwise, SO	3	6
InfiniWing	A modified beam used in beam trawling, that differs to a traditional beam in its hydrofoil design which serves to reduce the frictional resistance of the gear in the water and uses downthrust to keep the net on the bottom. Its centrally located foot acts as the sole point of contact with the seabed, reducing the footprint of the gear on the bottom & benthic impact. In doing so, it further decreases the gears drag, fuel consumption, and associated GHG emissions.	WFPO, Waterdance, Brixham Trawl Makers, HFK Engineering	4	7
InfiniDoor	Self-adjusting trawl doors that can maintain a given distance to the seabed, turning a bottom trawl into a semi-pelagic one. The control mechanism was previously developed and a prototype tested. A second generation will be developed which can operate at the slower speeds that are characteristic of demersal trawls.	DTU Aqua, MLD Aps, University of Çukurova	5	7
InfiniSort	Technology to individually move stunned and immobilized fish from a pile to a conveyor, for the purpose of implementing fish singulation on a conveyor belt. This enables individual scanning, sorting and processing according to species and/or weight.	SO, Melbu Systems	4	7
InfiniSile	Bioconversion of fish viscera from fish gutting into a product suitable for feed or as fertiliser. The process consists in an autolysis of fish viscera with their own endogenous enzymes and with	AZTI	5	7

	controlled pH. The process takes place in an onshore facility. Including the protocol for the collection, handling, preservation and storage of fish viscera on board. Also including the protocol for safe and secure landing of fish viscera in the harbour without interference with main products.			
InfiniFood	Seafood product for human consumption made from Non-Indigenous Species (NIS), based on adaptation or modification of current sausage production methods and developing additional value-added products such as fish sauce, paste, and kimchi.	CU, HCMR	5	7
InfiniGrow	Plant fertiliser based on fish silage obtained from fish viscera, remnants, and NIS that are not suitable for human consumption. Silage obtained through fermentation with formic acid will be mixed with salts containing zinc, iron, and manganese in proportions tailored to different plant needs. After developing the nutrient-enhanced silage using formic acid fermentation, the next phase will focus on validating its agricultural applications.	CU	4	7

3 Solution-specific testing plans

Within this section the detailed testing and validation plan for each of the ten solutions is presented. While the solutions differ substantially in technological nature, operational context, and maturity level, a common validation framework is applied to ensure methodological coherence across WP4 activities. The plans are organised according to four functional domains mentioned before.

For each solution, the testing strategy is described in terms of its operational context, testing objectives, data collection and analysis approach, and identified risks and mitigation measures. This structure ensures comparability across heterogeneous solutions while allowing sufficient flexibility to account for domain-specific technical and operational characteristics.

In addition to the solution-specific descriptions provided below, an overview of all 11 pilot cases is presented in Table 3-1. For each case, the table specifies the technology tested, the fisheries context, the geographical area, the operational environment (onboard and/or onshore), the extent of implementation, and the types of data collected. This consolidated overview clarifies how validation activities are distributed across fisheries systems and operational settings, and provides transparency regarding the scope and evidence base of the planned testing activities. As InfiniLog and InfiniCatch Jano are tested jointly within the same operational setting, they are presented in a single row and discussed together in Section 3.1.1, although they are counted as two separate pilot cases. Conversely, InfiniDoor is evaluated in two distinct pilot cases and therefore counted twice; however, its testing approach is described comprehensively in a single subsection (Section 3.2.2).

Table 3-1: Summary of WP4 pilot cases detailing technologies, fisheries settings, operational conditions, implementation scope, and data collection.

#	Solution	Fisheries	Area	Environment	Extent	Data collected
1	InfiniLog	Pelagic seasonal fisheries	Bay of Biscay	2 commercial fishing vessels	2-year testing period, spanning the full seasonal fishery cycle per vessel	VMS, fuel consumption, catch and environmental data...
2	InfiniCatch Jano					

3	InfiniCatch Trawl	Whitefish trawling	Northeast Atlantic	≥5 commercial fishing vessels	2–3 1-week trials per vessel, plus continuous monitoring	VMS, fuel consumption, environmental, winch cable load and drag, gear position
4	InfiniCatch NOR	Large-scale demersal and pelagic	Northeast Atlantic & North Sea	~10 commercial fishing vessels	Continuous from the second project year until project end	VMS, ERS, and catch data
5	InfiniWing	Demersal (beam) trawling	Celtic Sea	Commercial fishing vessel	Multiple trips over several months	Catch, fuel consumption, seabed contact (by proxy)
6	InfiniDoor	Whitefish trawling	Mediterranean and Black Sea	Commercial fishing vessel	8–10 days	Catch, seabed contact, drag, and fuel consumption
7	InfiniDoor	Nephrops trawling	North Sea and Skagerrak	Research vessel rigged for fishing	6–8 days	Catch, seabed contact, drag, and fuel consumption
8	InfiniSort	Danish seining, demersal whitefish	Northeast Atlantic (hardware test), Bay of Biscay (feasibility study, no hardware test)	Commercial fish processing plant, commercial fishing vessel	2–3 trials, each lasting 1 day	3D images, video
9	InfiniSile	Demersal trawling	Bay of Biscay	On-shore pilot facility	1–3 trials, each lasting 3–4 months	Process monitoring and product characterisation
10	InfiniFood	Small-scale fisheries	Mediterranean and Black Sea	Pilot plant	2–3 trials, each lasting 3–6 months	Product characterisation and

						consumer preferences
11	InfiniGrow	Small-scale fisheries	Mediterranean and Black Sea	Greenhouse	1-3 trials, each lasting 3-4 months	Product characterisation

3.1 Decision Support Systems (DSS)

3.1.1 InfiniLog & InfiniCatch Jano

Operational context

The testing of InfiniLog and InfiniCatch Jano will be conducted within pelagic seasonal fisheries, specifically targeting pole-and-line and trolling operations in the Bay of Biscay. The solutions will be evaluated on board two commercial fishing vessels over a period of two years, with each trial coinciding with the duration of the seasonal fisheries on each vessel.

Testing objectives

The main objective of the testing is to ensure that InfiniCatch Jano fulfils its intended purpose, namely providing fuel savings and greater operational efficiency, while remaining user-friendly to guarantee uptake and utilisation by fishers. Specific questions addressed during the test include determining the onboard and onshore configuration of sensors, hardware, and other components that best suit the tool's purpose; identifying the type of connection necessary to provide near-real-time information for operational decision-making; and assessing whether it is possible to deliver near-real-time information regarding the efficiency of a fishing event.

The expected outputs of the testing phase include the collection of new onboard datasets, a protocol for the installation of the solution, and feedback from end-users. The solution will be evaluated against a baseline consisting of data describing historical and current fishing behaviour, including elements used to construct and feed the DSS, as well as qualitative feedback gathered through interviews and surveys with the testing skippers regarding the usability and benefits of the system.

The feedback loop for solution improvement begins with the development of individual models contributing to the DSS using historical datasets to establish baseline AI algorithms for preliminary testing. During the trials, additional data collected on board will be used to refine and enhance the performance of these models. At the same time, the relevance and applicability of all system components will be evaluated in collaboration with end-users to ensure operational suitability. Following optimization of the individual models based on updated data and user requirements, they will be integrated into a unified model, which will form the core of the DSS. Finally, the DSS will undergo onboard testing, operating in near real-time via onshore AI servers to ensure robustness, scalability, and operational readiness.

Figure 3-1: Iterative AI model development and deployment cycle. Historical and new trial-vessel data feed the training of AI models, which are subsequently optimized, integrated into a unified solution, and deployed as onboard decision-DSS. The system continuously incorporates updated data to refine and improve model performance.

Data collection, management, & analysis

The data collection for InfiniCatch Jano will draw on both historical and new onboard sources. Historical datasets include Vessel Monitoring System (VMS), Automatic Identification System (AIS), or GPS vessel data, logbooks, oceanographic measurements (e.g., temperature, chlorophyll), official or estimated catches, fuel costs, fishing notes, and TAC information. On board, new data will be collected from VMS, AIS, or GPS vessel data, engine and vessel activity monitoring (including RPM, speed over ground, speed over water, bearing, and fuel consumption), and catch data derived from AI-powered computer vision.

The onboard electronic monitoring system, comprising Electronic Monitoring (EM) cameras and its retrieval network, will estimate real-time catches. Data will

be visualised on onboard devices and processed via an AI server, with all electronic devices connected through an NMEA network. Propulsion parameters such as temperature, RPM, fuel consumption, vessel position and speed, electrical generation, and additional variables including trim, heel, and distance travelled will be monitored using flow meters, tachometers, GPS, and clamp meters. All these data will be logged and transmitted by InfiniLog to cloud servers via internet connections including Starlink, WiFi, or 5G, allowing storage and exchange between vessels and onshore facilities.

The overall data quality will depend on the intrinsic characteristics of each dataset and sensor, including accuracy, precision, and spatiotemporal resolution. Because the project integrates heterogeneous data sources such as in situ measurements, onboard sensor streams, satellite observations, model outputs, and administrative datasets like logbooks, a tailored quality assurance approach will be applied to each dataset type. All datasets will undergo systematic preprocessing including detection and removal of outliers, noise filtering, gap handling, and elimination of duplicates. Additional consistency checks will verify spatial and temporal coherence, variable ranges, and internal structure.

Expected data quality will vary across sources. Environmental datasets, for example from the Copernicus Marine Service, generally undergo rigorous scientific quality control and provide explicit uncertainty estimates, offering high reliability. Logbook datasets often present inconsistencies such as duplicates or incomplete records and lack formal error estimates, requiring additional cleaning, cross-checking, and harmonisation. Onboard instrumental datasets provide direct measurements of real conditions, but may require calibration, drift correction, and verification procedures to ensure reliability over time. Each dataset will therefore follow a dedicated processing and validation pathway designed to maximise its quality according to its origin, limitations, and intended use within the testing and validation framework. All data management and quality procedures will follow the project's Data Management Plan and adhere to FAIR principles, ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and consistent handling across partners.

Analysis of the collected data will be conducted following a structured and harmonised workflow to ensure accuracy and comparability of the datasets. Given the diversity of data sources used in this pilot, the analytical approach will standardise processing steps while allowing flexibility to accommodate dataset-specific characteristics:

- Data preprocessing: All raw datasets will undergo an initial preprocessing phase to ensure internal consistency and readiness for analysis. This includes harmonising units and formats, aligning temporal and spatial references, etc.

- **Noise and outlier detection:** To improve the overall reliability of the datasets, statistical methods will be applied to identify and remove noise and outliers. Techniques such as smoothing filters, and spatiotemporal consistency checks will be used depending on the data source. All cleaning and correction procedures will be documented to preserve full traceability of the analytical workflow
- **Consolidation and analytical dataset preparation:** After cleaning, datasets will be integrated into consolidated analytical structures. This will include merging relevant data streams, generate derived variables, and ensuring that the resulting datasets are complete, coherent, and aligned with the iterative testing cycles between WP3 and WP4.
- **Model training and analytical evaluation:** Processed datasets will be used to train and validate models supporting the assessment of the technologies under real operational conditions. This includes splitting data into training, validation, and test sets, applying cross-validation schemes, and optimising model parameters. The analyses produced will feed directly into the performance evaluation and iterative improvement of the technologies throughout the project.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

Key risks associated with the testing include limited data availability and measurement uncertainty, which may constrain performance assessments. The installation of InfiniCatch Jano's associated sensors requires precise adaptation to vessel-specific conditions; any failure in sensor operation or data collection could lead to incomplete datasets, potentially affecting the robustness of subsequent analyses and the optimisation of the AI-driven decision support system.

To mitigate these risks, data collection will begin as early as possible and continue for the full duration of the fishing seasons to enhance algorithm robustness and reduce signal-to-noise effects. To minimize the risk of malfunctioning of sensors and data loss, a comprehensive approach that includes conducting thorough pre-installation checks and preparing backup components to reduce downtime in case of equipment failure, maximizing the duration of data collection, and developing standardized installation and calibration protocols will be implemented. Additionally, continuous monitoring systems with automated alerts will be deployed to detect sensor malfunctions in real time, enabling immediate corrective actions, while robust data storage and backup solutions will safeguard against permanent data loss.

All onboard testing will comply with ethical, legal, and regulatory obligations established under Horizon Europe, the European Union, and Spanish legislation. The activities follow principles of responsible research, data protection, maritime safety, and transparency. Testing is observational, does not alter fishing gears or fishing behaviour, and therefore minimises risks to crew, vessel operations, and the environment. Procedures will ensure safe installation of all devices and alignment with Spanish maritime regulations, guaranteeing that no system interferes with navigation, communication systems, or fishing manoeuvres. The use of onboard cameras and monitoring sensors will comply with GDPR (EU 2016/679) and the Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 (LOPDGDD). Any incidental personal data, such as images in which crew members could be identifiable, will be processed lawfully and only for explicit research purposes, ensuring minimisation, pseudonymisation or anonymisation wherever feasible, secure storage, controlled access, and clear information to crew on their rights and data handling. Testing activities also adhere to Spanish fisheries and maritime regulations, including permissions from vessel owners and compliance with technical and occupational safety requirements. Ethical approvals, data-protection notifications, and all vessel-level permissions required for the deployment of monitoring equipment will be obtained prior to the start of testing. Documentation on compliance, risk assessment, and procedures for handling sensitive data will be maintained throughout, and all activities will remain strictly civil, non-intrusive, and focused on energy-use optimisation and catch documentation.

Schedule

A total period of more than two years of trials is planned, from September 2025 to May 2029, fully aligned with the duration of the albacore fishing season period in the Bay of Biscay, and encompassing both the preparation of the testing activities and the subsequent validation phases.

The testing activities will be implemented in four phases as follows.

Phase 1: Preparation and installation (September 2025 to June 2026). This phase includes all preparatory, organizational, and technical activities required, preferably before the start of the first fishing season, though not necessarily. Preparatory and coordination activities include:

- Search for appropriate volunteer vessels for the testing phase, ensuring suitability regarding fishing method, space availability, and technical compatibility with InfiniCatch JANO and InfiniLog.

- Contact with vessel owners and skippers, including interviews to explain the objectives of the testing, and jointly plan installation and operational procedures.
- Onboard visits to assess first-hand the installation requirements, available physical spaces, existing electronics, cable routing options, potential limitations, etc.

The technical installation activities are:

- Onboard installation of all required sensors, including EM cameras, propulsion measurement devices (flow meters, tachometers), NMEA-connected navigation instruments, and any additional hardware necessary for data acquisition.
- Verification of the correct functioning of each sensor, synchronization and compatibility with the logging network and onboard configuration.
- Setup and installation of the InfiniLog, data-transfer and connectivity testing.
- End-to-end verification of the complete onboard equipment suite (sensors, computers, cabling, power supply, network, etc.), ensuring the system is operational before the fishing season begins.

The phase concludes only when all the equipments are tested, functional, and integrated into the vessel's operational workflow.

Phase 2: Initial testing (May–November 2026 – first albacore fishing season period). Note that the duration of the albacore fishing season is not fixed; it fluctuates annually based on several conditions, such as time of first appearance of the target species in the Bay of Biscay fishing areas, profitability of the season, timing of TAC exhaustion and subsequent closure of the fishery, etc. Activities in this phase include:

- First onboard deployments during albacore fishery
- Initial data collection: GPS/AIS, RPM, SOG, SOW, bearing, fuel consumption, EM-camera catch images, etc.
- Early evaluation of data transmission

Phase 3: Full validation trials (May–November 2027 – next fishing season). Activities in this phase include:

- Mature multi-sensor data collection
- Validation of the DSS using updated AI models trained with new datasets
- Assessment of robustness, fuel savings, and usability under real fishing scenarios

Phase 4: Final evaluation and system refinement (late 2027 till the end of the project). Activities in this phase include:

- Integration of all individual AI models into the unified DSS
- Onboard NRT DSS operation through onshore AI servers
- Evaluation with skippers

The timing of testing is strongly linked to external constraints, in particular the seasonal albacore fishery in the Bay of Biscay, as well as vessel availability and technical installation requirements. As a result, the testing windows are largely determined by fishing seasons and operational conditions.

If testing cannot proceed as planned, several fallback strategies are foreseen. These include shifting trials to the next available fishing season, extending the data collection period where possible, and postponing final system integration and validation into later project stages.

3.1.2 InfiniCatch Trawl

Operational context

InfiniCatch Trawl will initially be installed on research vessels and subsequently on commercial bottom trawlers, with potential applicability to pelagic trawlers. Testing will focus on bottom trawling operations, and large commercial freshwater and freezer trawlers. The geographical area for testing is the European Economic Area (EEA) of Iceland. Trials will involve two research vessels and five commercial trawlers. The duration of testing will extend from the installation of the system through to the end of the project, with the possibility of continuing beyond this period.

Testing objectives

The main objective of the testing is to iteratively develop and validate data collection, alignment, and storage methods as well as the AI models underpinning InfiniCatch Trawl. This will be done in close collaboration with industry partners within WP3, recognising that the way fishing gears are operated by captains can significantly influence outcomes. The AI algorithms will be progressively refined as additional data become available. In the first iteration, the focus will be on establishing efficient solutions for storing, transferring, combining, and analysing large volumes of real-time environmental and winch/gear data collected from vessels at sea, alongside ongoing software development to enable real-time decision-making support for captains.

In subsequent iterations, following additional installations and expanded data collection, demonstrations will support training and refinement of the algorithms embedded in the software interface. The objective is to reduce unwanted

environmental impacts, such as bycatch, seabed disturbance, or carbon emissions, while simultaneously lowering fuel and gear costs for the industry and improving usability through structured industry input. The expanded datasets will also enable analyses within WP5 to assess how different operational decisions influence fishery-wide efficiency.

The testing will address several specific questions: whether the input data are of sufficient quality for AI-driven decision recommendations; whether the models can accurately predict relevant gear states and operational outcomes; whether system recommendations lead to measurable improvements compared to current practice; whether recommendations are timely, explainable, and safe; and whether the system performs consistently across vessels and gear types while fitting within established user workflows.

Expected outputs of the testing phase include a tested and validated InfiniCatch Trawl prototype, real-world operational datasets to support AI development, verified performance metrics and robustness assessments, an AI-based decision-support algorithm with evaluated recommendations, structured user feedback and usability assessments, and technical documentation including updated TRL status.

The solution will be evaluated against a baseline reflecting current operational practice, including levels of situational awareness regarding trawl gear behaviour, the quality, timeliness, and consistency of operational decisions, the ability to optimise gear performance relative to standard practice, usability and operator workload compared to manual decision-making, and operational robustness across vessels, gear types, and environmental conditions.

Results from testing will be incorporated through an iterative feedback loop combining continuous data collection, algorithm development, expert validation, and model refinement. Initial algorithms will rely on a limited set of variables, with increasing complexity introduced as data volumes grow and results are validated by vessel operators. Feedback from captains, together with empirical test results, will guide adjustments to model structure and the integration of additional variables, ensuring continuous improvement and progressive strengthening of the decision-support system.

Data collection, management, & analysis

Data collected during testing will include both operational and technical components of the InfiniCatch Trawl solution, with core measurements encompassing VMS data, fuel consumption, environmental parameters, winch cable load and drag, and detailed information on gear position and geometry. The

system will also generate software source code for trawl data processing, modelling, and algorithm development, including both restricted and publicly available components. In addition, operational experience and opinion data from users will be logged to support usability assessment and iterative refinement.

Data are collected via two main channels integrated by the onboard Hafriti data logging system. NMEA sensor messages, aggregated to one-minute frequency, provide GPS position, depth, weather variables, vessel motion parameters, and winch measurements. In parallel, JSON-based telemetry from trawl-mounted acoustic sensors delivers per-minute information on otter door behaviour, net geometry, and codend characteristics. These streams are complemented by gear metadata from trip and station records, including vertical and horizontal opening, warp length, mesh size, bridle length, headline length, and otterboard characteristics.

The data collected during testing are expected to exhibit high overall quality, with vessel-mounted sensors providing consistently reliable coverage across key operational variables such as position, depth, environmental conditions, and winch activity. Gear-mounted acoustic sensors are anticipated to have lower coverage, reflecting occasional connectivity issues or sensor failures, particularly on certain components. Known data quality challenges include sporadic outliers for wind speed, acoustic measurement artifacts, and variability in tow duration arising from different operational protocols or conditions across trips.

The collected data provide a comprehensive, multi-sensor record of bottom trawl operations that is suitable for modelling trawl performance, energy efficiency, and the relationship between gear configuration, environmental conditions, and fishing outcomes. This will support iterative improvement of the InfiniCatch Trawl solution.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks associated with testing include technical failures, system reliability, prototype maturity, and stakeholder engagement. As the solution integrates multiple hardware and software components (such as sensors, data transmission systems, and AI models) equipment malfunctions, sensor failures, data loss, or software bugs could interrupt data collection or compromise data integrity. Several components remain in the prototyping phase, and interactions between hardware, software, and vessel-specific systems have not yet been fully validated under operational conditions, which could lead to unforeseen performance issues. Additionally, limited engagement or reduced cooperation from shipowners or

vessel crews could affect testing, particularly if installation, operational adjustments, or perceived short-term benefits are unclear.

To mitigate these risks, all hardware and software components will be pre-tested and validated before onboard installation, with clear protocols for troubleshooting, data backup, and system resets to minimise downtime or data loss. Testing will follow an incremental, iterative approach, starting with limited functionality and gradually increasing system complexity, using early feedback to refine hardware–software interactions and improve system stability. Engagement with shipowners and crews will begin early and continue throughout the project, with procedures designed to minimise disruption to normal fishing operations and user feedback actively incorporated to maintain motivation and ensure practical relevance.

Testing will be carried out in full compliance with Icelandic fisheries legislation and within the legal framework for commercial and research fishing. All trials onboard commercial vessels will operate under existing licences and quota allocations, with additional research permits obtained if required. As the solution involves data collection and decision-support functionality rather than experimental fishing gear, no additional ethical concerns regarding animal welfare or environmental impact are anticipated beyond those associated with standard fishing operations. Data ownership, access, and sharing will be governed by formal agreements with vessel owners, in accordance with Icelandic data protection law, ensuring that commercially sensitive information is handled confidentially and securely.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniCatch Trawl is planned to take place continuously from M1 to M48 (June 2025 – May 2029). Data collection, system development, and evaluation activities run in parallel throughout this period.

The testing is structured into three main phases. The first phase (M1–M18; June 2025 – November 2026) focuses on the installation of hardware and software components on vessels and initial functionality testing. The second phase (M1–M48; June 2025 – May 2029) consists of continuous data collection from both research and commercial vessels to support model development and validation. The third phase (M1–M48; June 2025 – May 2029) involves ongoing data dissemination and iterative use of collected data for system refinement.

The timing of testing is not linked to specific fishing seasons, production cycles, or other external constraints, as data collection is designed to be continuous and independent of seasonal variability.

No formal fallback timing is defined. However, deployment on additional vessels will occur on a rolling basis and depends on vessel availability in port and technician availability for installation. As this mainly affects expansion of data collection capacity, it does not impact the overall timeline.

3.1.3 InfiniCatch NOR

Operational context

The testing of InfiniCatch NOR will be conducted in two main regions: demersal trawl operations in the Northeast Atlantic, and pelagic trawl and purse seine operations in the North Sea. Approximately ten commercial fishing vessels will be involved, with trials carried out continuously from May 2026 to May 2029.

Testing objectives

The main objective of testing InfiniCatch NOR is to evaluate the performance of the newly developed decision-support algorithms in comparison to the existing Catchwise DSS and to operations without any DSS. This includes assessing potential reductions in fuel use and greenhouse gas emissions, using suitable proxies where direct measurement is not possible.

The testing will specifically address questions around the accuracy and robustness of the new algorithms, including estimated CPUE (catch per unit effort) and bycatch indicators, as well as their contribution to reducing search time, improving catch yields, and lowering fuel consumption. The usability and intuitiveness of the DSS for skippers before, during, and after fishing operations will be evaluated, along with how skippers build confidence in the system and how they perceive errors, such as false positives versus false negatives. Additionally, the testing will examine any discrepancies between modelled environmental data and actual onboard measurements and the impact of these discrepancies on decision-making.

Expected outputs include detailed catch and fuel usage records from the vessels, datasets comparing performance across the new DSS, existing DSS, and no-DSS scenarios, skipper feedback and usability assessments, and a comparison of measured versus modelled environmental data. Testing will be benchmarked against current Catchwise DSS performance and operations without any DSS. Feedback from skippers and analysis of operational data will inform iterative improvements, parameter adjustments, or further refinement of the algorithms.

Data collection, management, & analysis

Data collection during testing will draw on public Electronic Reporting Systems (ERS) and VMS data from the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, and will

possibly be supplemented by data from Catchwise customers participating in the trials. The predictions generated by the algorithms will also be recorded to enable comparison with actual outcomes. Additionally, ideally, the decision-making process of the skipper when using the new DSS features will be logged to provide operational context and insights into usability.

Catch data will be logged either directly on the vessel or retrieved from official logbooks or the Directorate, with no additional sensors required. Fuel consumption data will be collected via existing onboard systems, and vessel positioning can be accessed through Catchwise systems without the need for extra sensors. Environmental data, such as water temperature, may be manually recorded from trawley sensors, but this is not a primary focus.

As some erroneous reporting of registered catch data may occur, data quality will be ensured through preprocessing steps to remove obvious errors, such as anomalous positions, catch weights, or duplicate records. Environmental datasets will be checked for consistency, and temporal gaps will be addressed using alternative models or appropriate interpolation methods.

Analysis of the collected data will focus on comparing the performance of the new DSS, the existing DSS, and no-DSS scenarios, while accounting for differences in vessel size, catch efficiency, and other operational factors. Statistical methods will be applied to provide robust and confident evaluations of the DSS impact on catch efficiency. Skipper feedback will also be analysed to identify usability issues and guide further refinement of the system.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks associated with testing include the possibility that the new algorithms may exhibit poor predictive power in early stages, potentially leading skippers to make suboptimal decisions and reducing confidence in the Catchwise system overall. Another risk is misalignment of the development and testing schedule with fishing seasons, as missing the appropriate season could delay testing by up to a year. There is also a risk that the testing phase may not capture all relevant metrics or could have an overly narrow focus, particularly regarding verification of both catch performance and reductions in fuel consumption, energy use, and associated GHG emissions.

Mitigation measures include ensuring stakeholders (Catchwise customers) taking part in the testing are fully briefed on the nature of the new features and algorithms, and that the reliability has not been established. They also include careful planning, consulting with stakeholders, and holding realistic expectations

of what is possible. Finally, consideration will be given to what quantities need to be measured to ensure they are sufficient to substantiate the intended analyses.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniCatch NOR is planned to take place continuously between M12 (May '26) to M48 (May '29).

The testing follows a continuous and iterative approach rather than clearly separated phases. Activities include ongoing data collection from commercial vessels, evaluation of decision-support algorithms, and iterative refinement of model performance based on operational data and user feedback. Early stages are expected to focus on assessing algorithm performance and robustness, while later stages will emphasise comparative evaluation against existing systems and further optimisation.

The timing of testing is partly linked to fishing seasons, as the effectiveness of the algorithms depends on alignment with operational fishing activities. A key identified risk is misalignment with fishing seasons, which could delay testing by up to one year.

No explicit fallback schedule is provided, although mitigation measures highlight the importance of careful planning to ensure alignment with relevant fishing seasons.

3.2 Fishing gear

3.2.1 InfiniWing

Operational context

InfiniWing will be tested in the UK's South West beam trawl mixed fishery, operating on the rough, rocky and banking grounds that are typical for that area. The trials will involve the beam trawl fishing method and will be carried out within the "South West beamers over 250 kW" fleet segment. Testing will take place on board a commercial fishing vessel owned by Waterdance and affiliated with the South West Producers Organisation. A total of one vessel will participate in the trials. Data collection will take place over several months and across multiple fishing trips.

Testing objectives

The main objective of the testing is to assess the performance of InfiniWing under real fishing conditions and evaluate its operational efficiency at sea. In particular,

the trials will examine its performance in relation to handling, drag reduction, seabed contact, fuel consumption, and the resuspension of sediments and associated release of carbon into the water column.

The tests will address several specific questions regarding how InfiniWing affects commercial fishing operations when compared with a conventional beam trawl. These include evaluating differences in gear handling, the extent of drag reduction achieved, the level of seabed contact during fishing operations, the potential for fuel savings, and the extent to which the gear may reduce sediment resuspension and carbon release.

The data collected during testing will be used to generate a number of performance indicators. These include Fuel Use Intensity (FUI), defined as the litres of fuel used per kilogram of landed catch; Fuel Use Efficiency (FUE), defined as the litres of fuel used per unit of fishing effort; the ratio between the value of landings and the cost of fuel; and changes in benthic catch, which will be used as a proxy indicator for potential reductions in seabed impact, sediment resuspension, and associated CO₂ release.

InfiniWing will be evaluated against a conventional beam trawl routinely used by commercial vessels operating in the relevant fleet segment. This baseline provides a direct comparison with current fishing practices.

Throughout the testing period, the results obtained will inform potential refinements of the InfiniWing design. This iterative process will allow adjustments to be made to improve performance with respect to the selected operational and environmental indicators.

Data collection, management, & analysis

Data collection during the testing phase will focus on operational performance, fuel consumption, fishing activity, and catch composition in order to evaluate the effects of the InfiniWing design under real fishing conditions. The collected data will include the litres of fuel used during fishing trips and specifically during fishing operations, as well as the price of fuel used by the vessel. High spatio-temporal data on fishing activity will also be recorded. In addition, fish landing information will be collected by species, weight, and value at first sale. Catch data will include total catch information, including discards for selected key species per fishing operation, as well as estimates of mixed-species benthic catch per fishing haul.

To collect these data, an onboard fuel-use data logger will be installed to record fuel consumption during operations. Fishing activity and catch processing will be

monitored using an Anchor Lab Remote Electronic Monitoring (REM) system, which integrates a GPS sensor, video cameras, and a computer unit.

High data quality is expected from the monitoring systems used. The GPS component of the REM system will provide high-resolution information on fishing activity, while video footage will allow fishing operations to be verified. These data will be combined with the recorded fuel-use data to generate detailed estimates of fuel consumption during fishing operations. Fishing landings data will be obtained from official logbook records and complemented by the analysis of REM video footage of catches processed onboard. Established analyst protocols and quality control procedures will be applied to ensure the reliability of the catch, discard, and benthic catch data.

For data analysis, established protocols will be applied to the REM analyst data to generate haul-level estimates of retained landed catch, and benthic catch using routines programmed in R. Data on fishing activity, fuel use, and catches will then be used to calculate the defined performance indicators. These indicators will be explored at multiple scales, including the haul level, trip level, and across the full testing period. The results will be compared with equivalent data obtained from operations using a conventional beam trawl design in order to determine significant differences and assess the extent of those differences.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks related to the testing include potential failure of the InfiniWing design to the extent that it cannot be operated for several months on a commercial fishing vessel. Additional risks concern possible failure of the REM data collection system, the inability to analyse REM data to generate robust comparative catch data, and potential failure to collect fuel-use data through the onboard data logging technology.

Mitigation measures have been identified for each of these risks. An earlier version of the InfiniWing design has previously been used by the vessel involved in the trials, and the adjustments made to enhance its performance in the specific fishery are considered sufficiently moderate to expect that the updated design will operate effectively. Opportunities will also remain during the testing period to refine and adjust the design if required. Cefas has extensive experience using REM systems to generate catch and fishing activity data. The system will undergo technical testing before experimental data collection begins, and its functioning will be monitored throughout the testing period. In addition, a vessel-specific monitoring plan will be developed together with detailed protocols for fishers and REM data analysts to ensure that robust comparative catch data can be produced. This will

include analysing data from the first fishing trip to review the effectiveness of the defined protocols. Fuel-use logging technology will be tested onboard the vessel prior to the start of the InfiniWing trials, with data uploaded and reviewed to confirm that the system functions correctly before experimental data collection begins.

Regarding ethical, regulatory, legal, or permitting aspects, the REM system generates onboard video data that may include incidental footage of fishers. A specific Data Share Agreement will therefore be signed between the vessel company and the responsible institute, defining how the data will be used and confirming compliance with GDPR requirements. The InfiniWing gear design complies with existing technical fishing regulations and does not require any regulatory dispensation to operate.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniWing is planned to take place between project months M10 (March '26) and M34 (March '28).

The testing is structured into two main phases. The preparation phase (M10–M19; March '26 – December '26) includes installation of the REM system on the trial vessel, redesign of the InfiniWing based on previous iterations, and fabrication and delivery of the gear to the vessel's home port in Brixham. This phase is influenced by capacity constraints across multiple partners involved in design, installation, and manufacturing. The second phase (M20–M27; January '27 – August '27) consists of sea trials, during which the InfiniWing will be tested under operational conditions and compared against both a previous sumwing design and a standard beam trawl, with evaluation focusing on usability, fuel consumption, benthic impact, and catch performance.

The timing of the sea trials is linked to fishing seasons and operational constraints, including weather windows and availability of fishing opportunities.

If testing cannot proceed as planned, a fallback period is foreseen by postponing the sea trials to M27–M31 (August '27 – December '27).

3.2.2 InfiniDoor

Operational context

InfiniDoor will be tested in North Sea and Mediterranean demersal otter trawl fisheries, targeting whitefish and crustaceans. Testing will take place on board both commercial and research vessels, involving a total of two vessels. The trials are planned in three series: the first consists of four days of development at sea on a

research vessel, potentially split into two two-day cruises; the second comprises five days of fishing validation trials in the North Sea; and the third includes five days of fishing validation trials in the Mediterranean.

Testing objectives

The main objectives of testing are to develop and design the trawl doors, so they are capable of operating effectively at the slower towing speeds common in demersal otter trawl fisheries targeting whitefish and crustaceans, and to assess the fishing performance of gear equipped with InfiniDoor.

The specific questions addressed by the tests include whether InfiniDoor generates sufficient spreading forces at low speeds to maintain winghead spread and headline height compared to conventional bottom-contacting doors, whether the doors maintain their distance from the seabed at low towing speeds, and how the fishing performance of trawl gear with InfiniDoor compares to gear using conventional doors.

Expected outputs from testing include hydrodynamic lift and drag coefficients, assessment of gear geometry parameters such as headline height and door/wingend spread as functions of towing speed, and catch comparisons of main target species.

InfiniDoor will be evaluated against conventional seabed-contacting doors commonly used on demersal otter trawls. The feedback loop will combine analytic and numerical desk studies to identify potential new designs for testing at sea. An iterative approach is used during development trials, where rigging and operational settings are adjusted between deployments. To allow for structural modifications or optimization, subdividing trial durations may be necessary.

Data collection, management, & analysis

Data collected during testing will include detailed gear performance metrics, such as alongside catch composition and length measurements for target species. During development trials, tensions in sweeps and warps on either side of the trawl doors will be recorded using two 5-tonne Strainstall self-recording load cells, while towing speed through the water will be monitored with a Valeport Model 106 Current Meter. Gear geometry parameters, including headline height, wing spread, and door spread, will be captured using SIMRAD acoustic sensors. Door height above the seabed will be measured via altimeters, and sweep and groundgear contact will be monitored using Star Oddi tilt sensors. Underwater cameras will provide additional validation of gear performance and data accuracy. During the fishing trials, many of these measurements will be collected as well,

supplemented by detailed catch data collected after each tow, including species composition and length distributions.

Expected data quality is high, supported by well-maintained and calibrated instruments, with video observations serving as a cross-check to ensure the accuracy of sensor measurements.

Analysis of the collected data will employ a range of statistical methods. Mixed-effects models will be used to explore dependencies of load and gear geometry on operational parameters such as towing speed and tide direction. Catch comparison analysis will quantify relative changes in length-dependent catch efficiency between InfiniDoor and conventional doors, treating hauls as unpaired and applying bootstrapping to estimate 95% confidence intervals.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

Risks related to the testing primarily concern weather conditions, which can affect the scheduling and safety of fishing trials. Another key risk is potential instrumentation malfunction, as the trials depend on collecting a large amount of engineering data using a range of sensors and measurement devices.

Mitigation measures include maintaining flexibility in scheduling, allowing trials to be rescheduled in case of adverse weather. Instrumentation is kept well maintained and calibrated to minimize failures. In the event that critical data cannot be collected due to equipment malfunction, trials can similarly be rescheduled to ensure the completeness and reliability of the data.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniDoor is planned to take place between project months M10 (March '26) and M36 (May '28).

The testing is structured in four main phases. The development phase (up to M23; April '27) covers finalisation of the system design and preparation of prototype components. This is followed by engineering performance tests (M24–M25; May '27 – June '27), focusing on technical validation of hardware and software functionality under controlled conditions. The North Sea fishing performance tests (M27–M29; September '27 – November '27) will evaluate system performance under operational fishing conditions on commercial vessels. The final phase consists of Mediterranean trials (M34–M36; April '28 – May '28), assessing performance in a different regional and environmental context.

The timing of the testing is linked to seasonal and regional fishing operations. If testing cannot be completed within the planned timeframe due to operational, weather-related, or scheduling constraints, fallback periods are foreseen as

follows: engineering performance tests may shift to M27–M29 (September '27 – November '27), North Sea fishing performance tests to M34–M36 (April '28 – May '28), and Mediterranean trials to M40–M42 (October '28 – December '28).

3.3 Robotic fish handling

3.3.1 InfiniSort

Operational context

Initial hardware testing will be conducted in an on-shore whitefish processing plant in Northern Norway, followed by testing onboard a Danish seine vessel. Testing of the hardware is focussed on the singulation of live, stunned, and immobilized fish before scanning, catch registration, and subsequent processing. A case study will be performed in the Bay of Biscay, including both on-shore and onboard processing, without hardware testing in that region.

The trials will involve one Danish seine vessel, one on-shore processing plant in Northern Norway, and additional vessels and processing facilities in the Bay of Biscay. Each trial is expected to last approximately 2–3 days, though timing may be adjusted as needed.

Testing objectives

Initial tests use gutted and de-headed cod. Small-scale lab tests aim to verify system integration and core hardware and software functionalities, while assessing processing speed, accuracy, and robustness. Large-scale lab tests then focus on scaling the system to meet operational requirements. The first on-shore test evaluates whether the system works continuously under real-world operating conditions, identifies edge cases or problematic situations, and iterates to eliminate them. Subsequent tests, including a second on-shore test, use whole cod and whole whitefish to again verify continuous operation and address any remaining issues. Finally, a comparable onboard test is conducted on a Danish seine vessel to confirm system performance under operational conditions, following the same iterative approach.

The specific questions addressed at each stage include: whether all hardware and software components work together in small-scale lab tests; whether the system can achieve the required speed, accuracy, and robustness in large-scale lab tests; whether continuous operation is possible under real-world conditions with non-

live fish during on-shore trials; and finally, whether the system performs reliably on board with live, electro-stunned and immobilized fish.

Expected outputs from the testing phase include a system at TRL 7 suitable for continuous onboard operation, with documented validation through video recording of the tests. The solution is evaluated against the baseline of human fishers handling the fish. Feedback from each test iteration is used to identify slowdowns or failures, whether intermittent or systemic, to refine hardware and software and eliminate operational bottlenecks before the next phase of testing.

Data collection, management, & analysis

The data collected during testing will primarily consist of images and video of piles of fish, with additional catch data such as species and weight per individual fish where relevant. To capture this data, a RealSense or equivalent 3D camera will be used for image and video acquisition, while a CatchScanner system will collect species identification and individual fish weight. The resolution and frame rate of the 3D camera will define the expected data quality, and all sensors will be maintained and calibrated to ensure reliable recordings.

Analysis of the collected data will combine human inspection with automatic detection routines to identify failures in gripping or moving fish, as well as suboptimal speed during handling. The main objective is to evaluate the system's ability to transfer fish from a pile to a conveyor belt one-by-one. Success is assessed in a binary manner, while the speed of successful handling provides a secondary performance measure.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

Main risks associated with the testing include the unpredictability of the geometry and motion of fish piles, particularly during on-board trials. Mitigation measures include a gradual increase in test complexity, as describe before, beginning with controlled lab settings and scaling up to production-level hardware. On-shore trials will follow, allowing verification under realistic but safer conditions, before progressing to the full on-board environment.

Ethical, regulatory, and safety constraints require that the system maintains user safety around industrial robots within the limited space on-board the vessel. All trials will be supervised, ensuring operators are protected while interacting with the robotic systems.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniSort is planned to take place between project months M6 (January '26) and approximately M41 (December '28).

The testing is structured in several progressive phases, increasing in complexity and operational realism. The first phase consists of small-scale laboratory tests conducted in Q1 2026 (M6–M8; January '26 – March '26), focusing on verifying system integration, core functionalities, and identifying limitations in processing speed, accuracy, and robustness. This is followed by a second phase of large-scale laboratory tests between Q4 2026 and Q1 2027 (approximately M15–M20; October '26 – March '27), aimed at scaling the system and improving performance. Subsequently, two on-shore testing phases are foreseen at a whitefish processing facility. The first on-shore trial is planned by Q4 2027 (around M27; October '27 – December '27) and focuses on continuous operation under real-world conditions using processed fish. The second on-shore trial is expected around Q2 2028 (approximately M33; April '28 – June '28) and introduces whole fish representative of onboard conditions. The final phase consists of an onboard trial on a Danish seine vessel, planned for approximately Q4 2028 (around M39–M41; October '28 – December '28), to validate system performance in a full operational environment.

The testing schedule is not explicitly linked to specific fishing seasons but follows a staged development approach, progressing from controlled laboratory conditions to real-world onboard operations. No explicit fallback timing is provided.

3.4 Fish processing

3.4.1 InfiniSile

Operational context

The testing focuses on hake and will involve both demersal trawlers and longliners operating in the Bay of Biscay. Testing will be conducted on board commercial fishing vessels, as well as at an on-shore processing facility. The number of vessels involved is not yet finalized but will likely include one vessel conducting two successive catches, depending on the volume of fish required to carry out the fermentation trial. One trial will take place and cover the full process from the collection of fish viscera on board the vessel to the production of the fish hydrolysate on-shore.

Testing objectives

The main objectives of testing are to demonstrate the feasibility of collecting and landing fish viscera on board, identify the primary constraints for its practical application, and propose solutions. Additionally, the testing aims to verify the feasibility and scalability of the onshore valorisation process, assess the interest of the feed and fertilizer sectors in the final product, and define minimum quality requirements from potential users to incorporate into product specifications.

The specific questions addressed by this test include: determining the best method for handling and preserving fish viscera on board; assessing the capacity to process the actual volumes on shore; evaluating the time required for silage production to yield a valuable, acceptable product; understanding whether the product is of interest to local potential users; and identifying if further improvements are needed.

Expected outputs of the testing phase include a protocol for collecting, handling, and preserving viscera on board, an onshore setup and demonstration of a silage pilot, and a validated silage product data sheet based on feedback from potential users such as feed formulators, fishmeal producers, and fertilizer producers/users.

At present, the standard procedure for fish viscera is disposal at sea or conversion into fishmeal. This current practice provides a neutral point of comparison for assessing the potential benefits of the proposed handling and valorisation methods.

The feedback loop involves collecting input from fishermen regarding onboard management of viscera and from potential users of the silage product to guide modifications or further process steps.

Data collection, management, & analysis

During testing, data will be collected on fish viscera generation, handling, processing, and product characteristics. This includes fish viscera collection logs from the demersal fleet in the Bay of Biscay, as well as updated information on local generation of fish viscera and potential providers in local harbours.

For the silage process, the following process parameters will be recorded: temperature, pH, formic acid dosage, and storage time. The chemical composition of the silage will also be documented, including moisture, proteins, lipids, and micronutrient levels.

On board, a defined protocol for viscera collection and preservation will be applied, and viscera will be stored in closed containers or buckets. In the pilot plant, silage testing will follow a defined procedure using a food mill, a tank and

mixing system, a pH controlling system, a storage tank, and a laboratory for product analytics.

Data quality will be ensured through direct monitoring of the onboard viscera collection trial by a technician from AZTI. During the silage process, key process parameters (pH, temperature, and acid addition) will be controlled and monitored. The product will be analysed for basic composition and for specific parameters such as molecular weight profile and degree of hydrolysis (free amino acids).

The collected data will be validated with potential users.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks related to the testing include potential difficulties in collecting a relevant quantity of viscera and uncertainties regarding the availability of suitable local facilities in harbour for installing the pilot system. Limited volumes of raw material could affect the representativeness of the trial, while lack of appropriate infrastructure may delay or constrain pilot implementation.

Mitigation measures include scaling the process according to the volume that is realistically being landed, ensuring that the pilot reflects representative operational conditions. If necessary, other fisheries may be considered to secure sufficient raw material. In addition, installation of the pilot at AZTI's facilities (pilot plant) is foreseen as an alternative to harbour-based installation.

There are no specific ethical, regulatory, legal, or permitting constraints identified, as the raw material is currently a by-product that is discarded.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniSile is planned to take place between project months M08 (January '26) and M19 (December '26).

The testing is structured into five main phases. The preparation & equipment acquisition phase (M08–M12; January '26 – May '26) includes selection of vessels, coordination with onboard observers, preparation of equipment (IBC containers, agitator, gels), and set-up of the AZTI pilot area. This is followed by onboard viscera collection (M11–M16; April '26 – September '26), using hake from demersal trawlers, with the first significant collection planned for late April '26. The silage preparation phase (M12–M17; May '26 – October '26) consists of mincing, acidification to pH ~4, and controlled fermentation with periodic agitation. In parallel, monitoring and sampling activities (M12–M17; May '26 – October '26) include periodic pH checks and sampling for amino acid profile, molecular size distribution, hydrolysis degree, and allergen inactivation. The final evaluation

phase (M14–M19; July '26 – December '26) focuses on full characterisation of the silage product for feed and fertiliser applications, including stakeholder consultation.

Testing is linked to fishing activity of the Basque demersal trawler fleet, with higher predictability in spring periods when hake availability is higher. Onboard conditions such as limited freezing capacity may influence logistics, but both short-trip iced transport and longer frozen transport are feasible.

If viscera collection is delayed due to vessel availability, weather constraints, or logistics, fallback options include shifting the first large collection to M09–M10 (February '26 – March '26) or distributing smaller batches across summer and autumn. Analytical work can be delayed into early 2027 without affecting field operations, as it is not strictly dependent on collection timing.

3.4.2 InfiniFood

Operational context

The testing will take place within Mediterranean and Black Sea fisheries, focusing on the valorisation of non-indigenous species (NIS) into food products. The fisheries context includes Turkish bottom trawlers and Greek small-scale and purse seine fleets operating in the Mediterranean. Target species include Striped piggy (*Pomadasys stridens*) for the Turkish Case, and Lionfish (*Pterois miles*), Rabbitfishes (*Siganus* spp.), and Round herring (*Etrumeus golanii*) for the Greek Case. Processing will focus on fish sausage production methods (Türkiye) as well as additional food products such as fish sauce, fish paste, and kimchi (Greece). Testing will be conducted in the Mediterranean at pilot plant level. Two facilities will be involved, one in CU and one in HCMR, and 2–3 trials are planned, each lasting between three and six months.

Testing objectives

The main objective of the testing is to manufacture food products from NIS. The aim is to process and utilize these species as human food in order to create a supplementary income-generating activity for coastal communities, while simultaneously increasing their resilience to climate change.

The specific questions addressed by this testing include: What are the physicochemical properties of the meat obtained from NIS? Is this meat suitable for sausage manufacturing? What ingredients should be included in the fish sausage formulation? What are the quality properties of the fish sausage? Is the fish sausage produced from NIS acceptable to consumers? Are the additional fish

products acceptable to consumers, and which products are more appreciated? Is pilot-scale production and industrial preparation of these food products acceptable to professionals in the food service sector, and which products are most useful for them?

The expected outputs of the testing phase include data on the physicochemical properties of meat obtained from NIS, quality properties of fish sausage, and consumer preference data.

The solution will be evaluated against already available sausage production methods and NIS-based food products that have been tested in previous pilot studies. These existing methods and prior developments serve as the reference point for assessing improvements in formulation, processing performance, and product acceptance.

The feedback loop begins with the capture of different NIS from the Mediterranean and Black Seas. Physicochemical and toxicity analyses of the meat will be conducted, or past results reviewed, and used to determine the suitability of the raw material for sausage manufacturing and additional product development. These results will guide the formulation of the sausage and recipes for other food products. Once a preliminary formulation is defined, existing sausage production methods in the Pilot Sausage Plant at Çukurova University will be adapted or modified. Processing performance and final product characteristics will provide practical feedback for further refinement of formulations and processing parameters.

Consumer panel data will then be analysed to assess preferences, and these insights will inform improvements in product formulation, processing methods, and product selection, ensuring that the final solutions are technically suitable, culturally acceptable, and aligned with market expectations. For additional food products, feedback from professionals in the food sector, including aspects such as preservation methods and appearance, will also be considered to support commercialization potential and practical usefulness.

Data collection, management, & analysis

During testing, data will be collected on physicochemical properties of both raw material and produced sausages, toxicity analysis of the raw material, quality properties of sausages, and sensory analysis of sausages.

Thermocouples will be used to monitor cooking temperature changes, and a data logger will record fermentation temperature and humidity changes. Standard analysis protocols will be applied for physicochemical analyses, which will include determination of moisture content, fat, ash, pH, color values, texture profile

analysis (TPA), biogenic amine contents, and thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS). For the additional food products, microbiological evaluation will be performed, including total viable counts (TVC), *Enterobacteriaceae*, lactic acid bacteria (LAB), *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella* spp., to ensure product safety. Oxidative stability will be assessed through peroxide value and fatty acid profile determination. Freshness indicators specific to fish products, such as Total Volatile Basic Nitrogen (TVB-N) and trimethylamine, will be monitored. Shelf-life studies under controlled storage conditions will provide further information for formulation optimization.

Good quality data is expected, as the executing team is familiar with the instruments used and ensures that all equipment is properly maintained and calibrated.

The collected data will be statistically analysed to determine significant differences using analysis of variance methods and Duncan multiple comparison tests.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks related to testing include the suitability of the selected fish species for sausage manufacturing, potential malfunctioning of equipment in the pilot sausage plant, and cultural aspects related to fisheries and consumer preferences, such as hesitancy to try new fish species.

Mitigation measures include evaluating raw materials for sausage production through laboratory analyses (moisture, ash, fat, colour, TBARS, ...), followed by sausage manufacturing trials using the selected materials. For additional food products, suitability of the selected fish species has already been tested in past recipes, and existing experience will guide further development. Equipment in the laboratories is well maintained, and in case of malfunction, trials can be rescheduled. For additional food products, low-tech equipment is required, allowing flexibility in case of technical issues. Food products will be validated based on consumer preferences, reducing the risk of consumer hesitancy.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniFood is planned to take place between project months M02 (July '25) and M36 (May '28).

The testing is organised into four main phases. The preparation phase (M02–M12; July '25 – May '26) includes the collection of raw material from NIS and laboratory analyses to assess its suitability. This is followed by development trials (M12–M18; May '26 – November '26), focusing on the formulation of fish sausage products in the Turkish case study and additional fish products in the Greek case study at

small scale. Validation trials (M18–M30; November '26 – November '27) will include two to three pilot-scale production runs to manufacture fish sausage in the Turkish case study and additional fish products in the Greek case study, alongside consumer demonstrations. The final phase (M30–M36; November '27 – May '28) consists of data evaluation and reporting.

The timing of the testing is not linked to specific fishing seasons, production cycles, or other external constraints. No fallback timing has been specified.

3.4.3 InfiniGrow

Operational context

InfiniGrow will be tested within Mediterranean Sea small-scale fisheries, involving Turkish bottom trawlers and purse seine fisheries targeting NIS, with a focus on species such as Striped piggy (*Pomadasys stridens*). Silage obtained through fermentation with formic acid will be mixed with salts containing zinc, iron, and manganese, with proportions tailored to different plant needs. These products will be further tested under controlled environment conditions in a greenhouse. One facility will be involved. A total of one to three trials are planned, each lasting between three and four months.

Testing objectives

The main objective of the testing is the production of plant nutritional materials and fertilisers based on fish silage obtained from fish viscera, remnants, and NIS that are not suitable for human consumption.

The specific questions addressed include whether NIS-based fish silage is appropriate as a plant nutrition material that meets sustainability requirements, and what impact the developed plant nutrition material has on plant growth and nutrient uptake.

The expected outputs of the testing phase are nutrient-enhanced silage formulations produced through formic acid fermentation, and improved fish silage contributing to enhanced plant nutrition and nutrient availability.

The solution will be evaluated in comparison to conventional synthetic fertilisers used in agriculture. While synthetic fertilisers provide essential nutrients, fish silage represents a natural, organic alternative that supplies nutrients, supports soil microbial activity, repurposes waste materials, reduces environmental footprint, and aligns with circular economy principles in the fishing and farming industries.

The feedback loop begins with the development of nutrient-enhanced silage using formic acid fermentation, followed by validation of its agricultural applications. The resulting mixtures, rich in amino acid–microelement chelates and organic compounds, will be tested to assess their potential to improve plant nutrition. Greenhouse trials will compare the performance of these enriched silage formulations with conventional fertilisers. The results will determine the suitability of the silage for wider use in intensive plant production and guide further refinement to ensure it meets agricultural demands while offering a high-value alternative to traditional inputs.

Data collection, management, & analysis

During testing, data will be collected at two main stages: fish silage production and greenhouse trials.

For the NIS-based fish silages produced, initial analyses will include determination of amino acid profiles and plant nutrient element contents. After nutrient element supplementation, both nutrient element content and organic composition analyses will be performed. In the greenhouse experiments, plant growth parameters and nutrient element contents in plant tissues will be assessed.

In fish silage production, pH measurements will be conducted three times daily to ensure that the silage remains within the optimal pH range, preventing spoilage and preserving quality. Analyses of amino acid profiles and overall nutritional composition will also be carried out. The standard deviation associated with each measurement device will be considered to ensure accuracy and reliability.

In the greenhouse trials, pot experiments will be conducted under controlled greenhouse conditions. Plants will be fertilized with varying doses of essential nutrients such as N, P, and K, depending on the composition of the product(s) produced, to test their effectiveness. The product(s) will be applied either to the soil and/or as a foliar treatment. At the end of the trials, plant growth parameters, including yield and vegetative growth, will be measured, and nutrient element contents (uptake) in relevant plant tissues will be determined.

Regarding data quality, in fish silage production at least three parallel measurements will be conducted to validate the analyses. Different analytical instruments will be used for amino acid determination, and the resulting data will be compared to assess accuracy and consistency. The amino acid profile will be determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), and additional analyses will be performed using liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) to verify the results. Consistency with values reported in the literature will be considered essential.

In greenhouse trials, each treatment will include three replicates, following standard procedures in plant nutrition research. During nutrient element measurements via Inductively Coupled Plasma, standard plant samples will be analysed alongside experimental samples to validate accuracy.

For data analysis, during fish silage production no statistical software will be used; nutritional value, amino acid profiles, and pH measurements will be evaluated directly. In greenhouse trials, all experimental values will be subjected to one-way ANOVA. Significant differences will be identified, and Duncan's multiple comparison test will be applied when significant differences are observed.

Risks, constraints, & mitigation measures

The main risks related to testing include difficulty maintaining pH and ambient temperature within the desired range during silage production, potential technical problems in the greenhouse during the experiment, and variability in nutrient element contents in the final product, which could be either too low or too high.

Mitigation measures include frequent monitoring of pH and conducting fermentation under controlled temperature conditions to maintain product quality. Any technical issues in the greenhouse will be addressed promptly to ensure the experiment can proceed without disruption. Additionally, adjustments will be implemented as needed to achieve the desired nutrient element levels in the final product.

Schedule

The testing of InfiniGrow is planned to take place between project months M7 (December '25) and M36 (May '28).

The testing is structured in three main phases. The first phase (M7–M12; December '25 – May '26) focuses on fish silage production through formic acid fermentation and laboratory testing of the resulting material. The second phase (M13–M18; June '26 – November '26) involves the production of nutrient-enhanced silage through the addition of microelement salts tailored to plant requirements. The final phase (M19–M36; December '26 – May '28) consists of greenhouse trials, including two trials of approximately four months each, to evaluate the effectiveness of the developed products in comparison with conventional fertilisers. Testing is scheduled during mid-autumn and mid-spring to avoid excessively high summer temperatures in Adana.

If testing cannot be completed within the planned timeframe, a fallback period is foreseen between M37 and M42 (June '28 – November '28).

4 Conclusion

4.1 General findings

Across the 11 pilot cases, testing activities consistently integrate iterative development, operational validation, and user feedback to ensure practical applicability of each solution. Several pilots combine onboard and onshore activities, or lab-to-field trials, allowing robust evaluation under real-world conditions. Data collection is extensive, leveraging both historical datasets and newly generated operational data, including environmental measurements, gear performance, catch composition, or product quality metrics. Quality assurance and preprocessing steps are applied systematically to maximise reliability and comparability across heterogeneous datasets. Feedback loops are implemented across pilots, linking data collection to model refinement, technical optimization, and stakeholder input. This iterative approach supports the continuous improvement of performance, usability, and alignment with operational needs.

4.2 Challenges & risks

Common challenges include technical malfunctions, sensor reliability, environmental variability, and limited material availability. Data completeness and accuracy are recurring concerns, particularly when integrating multiple data streams or relying on heterogeneous sensors. Operational constraints such as seasonal windows, weather conditions, or vessel-specific limitations can affect testing schedules. For solutions involving biological or food products, additional risks include variability in raw material quality and potential mismatches with end-user requirements. Mitigation measures generally rely on early and continuous monitoring, iterative testing with controlled scaling, flexible scheduling, robust data management, and proactive engagement with end-users and vessel crews.

4.3 Overview of schedules

Finally, table 4-1 represents an overview of the proposed schedules for testing for each of the ten solutions of Infinifish. It summarises the key timing information provided in the previous sections in a harmonised format for ease of reference.

Table 4-1: Overview of the testing schedules for each of the ten solutions

Solution	Time frame	Testing phase(s)	Link to seasons/cycles/...	Fallback time frame
InfiniLog & InfiniCatch Jano	M4-M48	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Preparation and installation; M4-M13 2) Initial testing; M12-M18 3) Full validation testing; M24-M30 4) Final evaluation and system refinement; M31-m48 	Yes, linked to fishing seasons, vessel availability and technical dependencies	Either shift to next fishing season, extend data collection window, or prolong final integration period
InfiniCatch Trawl	M1-M48	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Installation & functionality testing; M1-M18 2) Data collection; M1-M48 3) Data dissemination; M1-M48 	No	Rolling implementation on additional vessels (no fixed fallback)
InfiniCatch NOR	M12-M48	Continuous iterative testing and model refinement	Yes – dependent on fishing seasons	NA
InfiniWing	M10-M27	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Preparation; M10-M19 2) Sea trials; M20-M27 	Linked to fishing seasons and weather windows	M27-M31
InfiniDoor	M10-M36	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Development phase; up to M23 2) Engineering performance tests; M24-M25 3) North Sea fishing performance tests; M27-M29 4) Mediterranean trials; M34-M36 	Linked to regional fishing seasons	Engineering: M27-M29; North Sea: M34-M36; Mediterranean: M40-M42
InfiniSort	M6-M41	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Laboratory tests, small-scale; M6-M8 2) Laboratory tests, large-scale; M15-M20 3) On-shore trial I; around M27 	None	Not specified

		4) On-shore trial II; around M33 5) On-board trial; M39-M41		
InfiniSile	M8-M19	1) Preparation & equipment acquisition; M8-M12 2) On-board viscera collection; M11-M16 3) Silage preparation; M12-17 4) Monitoring & sampling; M12-17 5) Final evaluation; M14-M19	Linked to demersal trawling activity (hake availability; spring peak)	Collection shift M09–M10 or distributed summer/autumn batches; lab work shift to early '27
InfiniFood	M2-M36	1) Preparation phase; M2-M12 2) Development trials; M12-M18 3) Validation trials; M18-M30 4) Evaluation and reporting; M30-M36	None	Not specified
InfiniGrow	M7–M36	1) Fish Silage Production; M7–M12 2) Nutrient-enhanced silage production; M13–M18 3) Greenhouse trials; M19–M36	Testing takes place from mid-autumn to mid-spring to avoid hot weather	M37-M42